

Supplementary Material for HEaAN.MLIR: An Optimizing Compiler for Fast Ring-based Homomorphic Encryption

1 THE ALGORITHM FOR FINDING RELAXED MODULUS FACTORS

Alg. 1 illustrates the static analysis for determining relaxed modulus factors in Sec. 6.1. The algorithm computes relaxed modulus factors in the reverse topological order, following the rules outlined in Table 1 of the paper.

Algorithm 1: Finding Relaxed Modulus Factors

Input: DAG of instructions and def-uses $G(N, E)$
Initial modulus factors $(f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n)$
Output: Relaxed modulus factors $(f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n)$

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1  $(p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n) \leftarrow \text{topological\_sort}(G)$ 
2 for  $i = p_n, p_{n-1}, \dots, p_2, p_1$  do
3    $f_i \leftarrow \min(\{f_i\} \cup \{f_{i'}^{i'} : (i, i') \in E\})$ 
4   Compute  $f_j^i$  for each  $(j, i) \in E$ , according to the Table 1 in the paper
5 end
6 return  $(f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n)$ 
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Fig. 1. The algorithm to find the maximally relaxed modulus factor of each instruction

2 THE BENCHMARK RESULTS

As we described at the Sec. 7, we used three different machines for the benchmark evaluations:

- (1) ARMv8.1 Cavium ThunderX2(R) CPU CN9980 @ 2.2GHz, 2 sockets ($128 \times 2 = 256$ threads) with 128GB RAM
- (2) Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6248 CPU @ 2.50GHz, 2 sockets ($40 \times 2 = 80$ threads) with 1TB RAM
- (3) AMD Ryzen Threadripper 2990WX (32 threads) with 128GB RAM.

We used HEaAN [1] and SEAL 4.0.0 [2] as competitors.

2.1 Single-Thread Performance of HE Operations

The tables 1 and 2 refer to the benchmark results of CKKS and BFV schemes, respectively.

Operation	Parameter	ARM			AVX-512			AMD			
		HEaaN	HEaaN.MLIR	Speedup (%)	HEaaN	HEaaN.MLIR	Speedup (%)	HEaaN	HEaaN.MLIR	Speedup (%)	
decode	FVa	39,297	45,505	-13.6	13,258	9,250	43.3	19,840	11,950	66.0	
decrypt		44,721	35,849	24.7	15,129	12,777	18.4	17,813	12,901	38.1	
decrypt & decode		79,526	41,823	90.1	30,062	12,252	145.4	36,540	11,935	206.2	
encode & encrypt-symkey		587,035	537,571	9.2	197,821	213,703	-7.4	315,364	294,545	7.1	
encode & encrypt-pubkey		922,756	759,474	21.5	240,980	179,570	34.2	464,964	416,238	11.7	
encode		68,017	40,859	66.5	36,134	17,437	107.2	41,351	20,540	101.3	
encrypt-symkey		342,137	322,849	6.0	126,423	168,035	-24.8	189,949	176,030	7.9	
encrypt-pubkey		703,367	657,506	7.0	173,631	145,056	19.7	338,768	311,307	8.8	
mult-without-rescale		2,395,569	2,284,531	4.9	650,165	591,461	9.9	1,274,213	1,145,879	11.2	
relinearize		2,312,815	2,142,437	8.0	515,802	536,554	-3.9	1,233,721	1,061,488	16.2	
rescale		208,979	195,652	6.8	54,991	44,691	23.0	101,240	99,533	1.7	
rotate-left		2,253,724	2,141,051	5.3	523,346	503,350	4.0	1,239,953	1,047,793	18.3	
decode		ST19	8,226	10,033	-18.0	2,276	1,461	55.8	4,267	2,474	72.5
decrypt			5,962	4,481	33.1	1,779	1,640	8.5	2,919	2,149	35.8
decrypt & decode	13,760		9,357	47.1	4,486	1,836	144.3	7,099	2,589	174.2	
encode & encrypt-symkey	74,667		80,780	-7.6	25,543	33,414	-23.6	46,417	46,588	-0.4	
encode & encrypt-pubkey	120,420		107,597	11.9	30,248	23,850	26.8	68,485	60,305	13.6	
encode	12,233		6,822	79.3	5,755	2,562	124.6	7,570	3,501	116.2	
encrypt-symkey	44,097		49,699	-11.3	15,317	26,256	-41.7	26,411	28,906	-8.6	
encrypt-pubkey	87,390		94,382	-7.4	20,570	19,186	7.2	48,563	46,956	3.4	
mult-without-rescale	780,203		852,392	-8.5	220,894	209,335	5.5	430,514	420,215	2.5	
relinearize	768,070		833,151	-7.8	199,921	201,745	-0.9	422,296	413,671	2.1	
rescale	23,510		27,558	-14.7	6,844	5,938	15.3	14,840	14,782	0.4	
rotate-left	773,405		790,675	-2.2	201,779	171,781	17.5	424,013	414,247	2.4	
decode	ST7		8,158	10,069	-19.0	2,298	1,493	53.9	4,093	2,438	67.9
decrypt			2,471	1,857	33.1	584	668	-12.6	1,163	958	21.4
decrypt & decode		9,069	8,903	1.9	3,017	1,831	64.8	5,398	2,621	106.0	
encode & encrypt-symkey		32,890	33,911	-3.0	11,740	13,739	-14.5	21,641	19,567	10.6	
encode & encrypt-pubkey		49,673	44,808	10.9	12,976	9,766	32.9	30,637	25,983	17.9	
encode		7,322	3,779	93.8	3,498	1,426	145.3	4,910	1,923	155.3	
encrypt-symkey		18,245	19,566	-6.8	6,677	10,949	-39.0	11,645	11,744	-0.8	
encrypt-pubkey		34,648	38,164	-9.2	7,999	7,647	4.6	20,864	20,099	3.8	
mult-without-rescale		87,833	85,310	3.0	26,860	20,732	29.6	52,784	45,022	17.2	
relinearize		82,723	80,295	3.0	19,859	17,753	11.9	50,157	42,608	17.7	
rescale		9,021	10,778	-16.3	2,538	1,709	48.5	5,672	5,713	-0.7	
rotate-left		84,037	81,514	3.1	20,925	18,262	14.6	50,537	43,061	17.4	
Average							11.8			29.1	37.3

Table 1. The wall time values of CKKS using a single thread, comparing the performance of HEaaN.MLIR with HEaaN. All wall time values are expressed in microseconds (μ s), except for the speedups (%).

Operation	Parameter	ARM			AVX-512			AMD		
		SEAL	HEaaN.MLIR	Speedup (%)	SEAL	HEaaN.MLIR	Speedup (%)	SEAL	HEaaN.MLIR	Speedup (%)
decrypt & decode	n=4096	917	771	18.9	204	141	44.7	470	445	5.6
encode & encrypt-pubkey		2,680	1,815	47.7	858	644	33.2	1,484	1,007	47.4
mult (w/o relinearize)		8,428	6,829	23.4	2,472	1,316	87.8	4,255	3,907	8.9
decrypt & decode	n=16384	13,066	11,787	10.9	2,501	1,969	27.0	6,216	6,447	-3.6
encode & encrypt-pubkey		26,910	20,398	31.9	7,414	4,677	58.5	15,011	10,547	42.3
mult (w/o relinearize)		145,858	133,886	8.9	43,810	31,432	39.4	72,075	72,897	-1.1
Average				23.6			48.4			16.6

Table 2. The wall time values of BFV using a single thread, comparing the performance of HEaaN.MLIR with SEAL. All wall time values are expressed in microseconds (μ s), except for the speedups (%).

2.2 Multi-Threads Performance of HE Operations

The tables 3 and 4 refer to the benchmark results of CKKS and BFV schemes, respectively.

Operation	Parameter	ARM			AVX-512			AMD		
		HEaaN	HEaaN.MLIR	Speedup (%)	HEaaN	HEaaN.MLIR	Speedup (%)	HEaaN	HEaaN.MLIR	Speedup (%)
decode		97,416	28,433	242.6	29,604	8,886	233.2	20,979	7,394	183.7
decrypt		9,188	8,772	4.7	3,280	2,964	10.7	4,752	4,063	17.0
decrypt & decode		88,625	30,076	194.7	30,398	11,409	166.4	25,243	7,663	229.4
encode & encrypt-symkey		94,413	71,423	32.2	46,534	28,513	63.2	41,266	19,869	107.7
encode & encrypt-pubkey		173,045	89,407	93.5	71,269	33,981	109.7	57,145	33,150	72.4
encode	FVa	22,850	14,107	62.0	23,547	7,421	217.3	18,355	6,421	185.9
encrypt-symkey		57,153	33,741	69.4	24,585	16,475	49.2	19,938	11,099	79.6
encrypt-pubkey		125,282	75,247	66.5	40,549	17,101	137.1	38,227	25,154	52.0
mult-without-rescale		217,525	238,483	-8.8	77,691	82,348	-5.7	126,862	126,574	0.2
relinearize		191,268	220,807	-13.4	94,706	86,472	9.5	122,371	109,636	11.6
rescale		29,210	33,417	-12.6	5,841	9,563	-38.9	9,681	10,896	-11.2
rotate-left		201,884	233,729	-13.6	72,615	80,806	-10.1	121,690	116,511	4.4
decode		22,351	6,268	256.6	4,138	1,452	185.0	4,093	1,374	197.9
decrypt		1,750	1,491	17.4	425	627	-32.2	320	317	0.9
decrypt & decode		20,708	6,656	211.1	4,832	1,878	157.3	5,134	1,593	222.3
encode & encrypt-symkey		20,061	14,389	39.4	8,034	4,524	77.6	7,150	3,574	100.1
encode & encrypt-pubkey		30,397	19,574	55.3	11,320	4,399	157.3	9,920	4,683	111.8
encode	ST19	5,591	2,927	91.0	3,840	2,191	75.3	3,614	1,305	176.9
encrypt-symkey		11,759	7,544	55.9	3,805	4,569	-16.7	2,894	1,773	63.2
encrypt-pubkey		22,260	13,366	66.5	6,202	3,561	74.2	6,083	3,023	101.2
mult-without-rescale		59,265	199,711	-70.3	18,501	37,575	-50.8	30,211	45,439	-33.5
relinearize		48,398	139,894	-65.4	18,612	37,869	-50.9	28,778	43,457	-33.8
rescale		5,865	7,238	-19.0	1,139	1,357	-16.1	1,444	1,661	-13.1
rotate-left		87,848	162,898	-46.1	18,857	37,921	-50.3	28,821	44,306	-35.0
decode		22,756	6,299	261.3	4,111	1,420	189.5	4,102	1,304	214.6
decrypt		1,519	1,341	13.3	283	317	-10.7	302	342	-11.7
decrypt & decode		19,937	6,403	211.4	4,239	1,623	161.2	4,612	1,601	188.1
encode & encrypt-symkey		20,079	13,067	53.7	7,233	4,065	77.9	6,917	3,306	109.2
encode & encrypt-pubkey		27,604	16,843	63.9	11,411	3,688	209.4	9,274	4,410	110.3
encode	ST7	5,261	2,640	99.3	3,713	1,208	207.4	3,606	1,024	252.1
encrypt-symkey		12,161	6,457	88.3	3,357	2,745	22.3	2,912	1,628	78.9
encrypt-pubkey		23,308	11,743	98.5	5,849	3,919	49.2	5,278	3,270	61.4
mult-without-rescale		21,300	26,292	-19.0	8,966	8,241	8.8	6,822	7,057	-3.3
relinearize		19,137	24,847	-23.0	4,031	4,818	-16.3	6,490	6,587	-1.5
rescale		5,483	6,736	-18.6	954	1,156	-17.5	1,431	1,578	-9.3
rotate-left		20,120	25,348	-20.6	7,025	5,285	32.9	7,038	6,864	2.5
Average				58.8			65.7			77.3

Table 3. The wall time values of CKKS using multiple threads, comparing the performance of HEaaN.MLIR with HEaaN. All wall time values are expressed in microseconds (μs), except for the speedups (%).

Operation	Parameter	ARM			AVX-512			AMD		
		SEAL	HEaaN.MLIR	Speedup (%)	SEAL	HEaaN.MLIR	Speedup (%)	SEAL	HEaaN.MLIR	Speedup (%)
decrypt & decode	n=4096	2,612	1,286	103.1	420	261	60.9	473	361	31.0
encode & encrypt-pubkey		5,396	8,114	-33.5	1,814	3,507	-48.3	1,500	3,003	-50.0
mult (w/o relinearize)		10,733	8,364	28.3	4,292	3,310	29.7	4,262	2,645	61.1
decrypt & decode	n=16384	14,522	6,856	111.8	3,374	1,365	147.2	6,157	1,740	253.9
encode & encrypt-pubkey		29,751	27,571	7.9	9,065	14,159	-36.0	14,820	11,130	33.2
mult (w/o relinearize)		145,700	49,298	195.5	45,716	15,029	204.2	72,204	15,874	354.9
Average				68.9			59.6			114.0

Table 4. The wall time values of BFV using multiple threads, comparing the performance of HEaaN.MLIR with SEAL. All wall time values are expressed in microseconds (μs), except for the speedups (%).

2.3 Impact of Optimizations

To evaluate the effectiveness of the compiler optimizations outlined in Sec. 6, we conducted measurements of single-core wall times of operations. As described in Sec. 7.4, we disabled three optimizations sequentially for this purpose.

- (1) Finding the best loop optimization strategy (Sec. 6.3)
- (2) Relaxing the modulus policy (Sec. 6.1)
- (3) Loop fusion (Sec. 6.2).

The following numbers are measured from the device (1) (Table 5), (2) (Table 6) and (3) (Table 7) respectively.

REFERENCES

- [1] HEaaN 2022. *HEaaN*. <https://heaan.it/>
- [2] SEAL 2022. Microsoft SEAL (release 4.0). <https://github.com/Microsoft/SEAL>. Microsoft Research, Redmond, WA..

Scheme	Operation	Parameter	HEaAN.MLIR		Disabling (1)		Disabling (1), (2)		Disabling (1), (2), (3)		
			Wall time	Slowdown (%)	Wall time	Slowdown (%)	Wall time	Slowdown (%)	Wall time	Slowdown (%)	
CKKS	decode	FVa	45,880	44,890	-2.2	45,407	-1.0	46,023	0.3		
	decrypt		34,027	36,663	7.7	37,570	10.4	47,852	40.6		
	decrypt & decode		41,746	42,955	2.9	43,947	5.3	83,082	99.0		
	decrypt-sum		230,402	277,462	20.4	284,202	23.4	330,461	43.4		
	encode & encrypt-symkey		528,844	552,388	4.5	560,040	5.9	688,536	30.2		
	encode & encrypt-pubkey		751,944	846,583	12.6	856,250	13.9	1,019,559	35.6		
	encode		40,272	39,017	-3.1	39,851	-1.0	121,406	201.5		
	encrypt-symkey		320,192	325,390	1.6	323,784	1.1	350,459	9.5		
	encrypt-pubkey		646,994	646,369	-0.1	651,557	0.7	738,366	14.1		
	mod-down		715,101	815,738	14.1	836,668	17.0	891,213	24.6		
	mod-up		1,096,416	1,201,276	9.6	1,245,006	13.6	1,613,104	47.1		
	mult-eval-key		256,582	331,584	29.2	338,060	31.8	788,693	207.4		
	mult-without-rescale		2,280,379	2,563,904	12.4	2,695,526	18.2	3,631,059	59.2		
	relinearize		2,112,296	2,445,664	15.8	2,538,106	20.2	3,429,856	62.4		
	rescale		198,540	217,978	9.8	217,696	9.6	242,251	22.0		
	rotate-left		2,141,913	2,415,654	12.8	2,552,213	19.2	3,448,498	61.0		
	tensor		70,613	89,143	26.2	85,664	21.3	171,861	143.4		
	CKKS		decode	ST19	10,029	9,958	-0.7	10,051	0.2	9,983	-0.5
			decrypt		4,317	4,234	-1.9	4,381	1.5	4,718	9.3
			decrypt & decode		9,354	9,837	5.2	9,892	5.8	13,728	46.8
decrypt-sum		33,303	41,809		25.5	42,660	28.1	43,196	29.7		
encode & encrypt-symkey		81,371	84,873		4.3	85,925	5.6	90,450	11.2		
encode & encrypt-pubkey		108,873	122,564		12.6	123,732	13.6	131,663	20.9		
encode		6,892	6,743		-2.2	6,718	-2.5	9,100	32.0		
encrypt-symkey		49,562	49,984		0.9	49,333	-0.5	50,750	2.4		
encrypt-pubkey		94,755	93,977		-0.8	93,309	-1.5	97,948	3.4		
mod-down		60,190	66,953		11.2	67,020	11.3	69,794	16.0		
mod-up		535,439	588,223		9.9	584,886	9.2	634,778	18.6		
mult-eval-key		174,194	249,438		43.2	229,179	31.6	591,145	239.4		
mult-without-rescale		842,391	971,529		15.3	968,589	15.0	1,444,438	71.5		
relinearize		824,461	954,711		15.8	949,245	15.1	1,423,343	72.6		
rescale	27,651	30,965	12.0	31,226	12.9	31,759	14.9				
rotate-left	829,329	958,623	15.6	915,752	10.4	1,500,260	80.9				
tensor	11,022	14,050	27.5	13,562	23.0	21,086	91.3				
CKKS	decode	ST7	10,045	10,032	-0.1	10,059	0.1	9,988	-0.6		
	decrypt		1,729	1,853	7.2	1,892	9.4	2,024	17.1		
	decrypt & decode		8,901	9,357	5.1	9,383	5.4	10,488	17.8		
	decrypt-sum		12,246	16,307	33.2	16,553	35.2	16,343	33.5		
	encode & encrypt-symkey		34,052	35,696	4.8	36,125	6.1	35,733	4.9		
	encode & encrypt-pubkey		45,023	50,926	13.1	51,421	14.2	52,480	16.6		
	encode		3,791	3,810	0.5	3,794	0.1	4,359	15.0		
	encrypt-symkey		19,759	19,650	-0.6	19,598	-0.8	20,397	3.2		
	encrypt-pubkey		38,319	37,675	-1.7	37,785	-1.4	38,880	1.5		
	mod-down		34,765	41,035	18.0	41,940	20.6	42,879	23.3		
	mod-up		34,680	39,993	15.3	40,618	17.1	55,018	58.6		
	mult-eval-key		10,402	12,461	19.8	13,617	30.9	32,074	208.3		
	mult-without-rescale		85,695	101,928	18.9	103,710	21.0	139,770	63.1		
	relinearize		81,386	95,167	16.9	97,237	19.5	133,247	63.7		
rescale	10,557	12,046	14.1	12,046	14.1	12,411	17.6				
rotate-left	82,082	96,630	17.7	98,705	20.3	138,719	69.0				
tensor	4,131	5,476	32.6	5,184	25.5	6,452	56.2				
BFV	decrypt & decode	n=4096	774	834	7.8	868	12.1	862	11.4		
	encode & encrypt-pubkey		1,811	1,815	0.2	1,828	0.9	1,956	8.0		
	FastBConvSk		202	202	0.0	206	2.0	211	4.5		
	FastFloor		171	170	-0.6	176	2.9	182	6.4		
	mult (w/o relinearize)		6,360	7,017	10.3	7,237	13.8	7,752	21.9		
	SmMRQ	95	95	0.0	95	0.0	95	0.0			
	decrypt & decode	n=16384	11,742	12,622	7.5	12,976	10.5	12,789	8.9		
	encode & encrypt-pubkey		19,910	21,459	7.8	21,082	5.9	26,456	32.9		
	FastBConvSk		6,030	6,055	0.4	6,104	1.2	6,076	0.8		
	FastFloor		5,425	5,398	-0.5	5,586	3.0	5,691	4.9		
mult (w/o relinearize)	133,303		147,149	10.4	148,631	11.5	151,311	13.5			
SmMRQ	1,005	1,009	0.4	1,007	0.2	996	-0.9				
Average					9.9		10.9		41.9		

Table 5. On the device ARMv8.1 Cavium ThunderX2(R) CPU CN9980 @ 2.2GHz with 128GB RAM, single thread speed of operations after sequentially disabling three optimizations: (1) finding the best loop optimization strategy (Sec. 6.3), (2) relaxing the modulus policy (Sec. 6.1), and (3) loop fusion (Sec. 6.2). All wall time values are expressed in microseconds (μ s), except for the slowdowns (%).

Scheme	Operation	Parameter	HEaAN.MLIR		Disabling (1)		Disabling (1), (2)		Disabling (1), (2), (3)		
			Wall time	Slowdown (%)	Wall time	Slowdown (%)	Wall time	Slowdown (%)	Wall time	Slowdown (%)	
CKKS	decode	FVa	8,473	8,380	-1.1	8,274	-2.3	8,194	-3.3		
	decrypt		13,584	13,041	-4.0	13,050	-3.9	17,026	25.3		
	decrypt & decode		10,590	10,489	-1.0	9,907	-6.4	31,746	199.8		
	decrypt-sum		49,672	66,242	33.4	66,324	33.5	71,383	43.7		
	encode & encrypt-symkey		212,770	206,667	-2.9	266,530	25.3	288,567	35.6		
	encode & encrypt-pubkey		195,383	185,613	-5.0	185,835	-4.9	271,449	38.9		
	encode		17,720	17,240	-2.7	17,126	-3.4	69,093	289.9		
	encrypt-symkey		170,738	165,369	-3.1	184,921	8.3	163,405	-4.3		
	encrypt-pubkey		145,022	146,981	1.4	144,703	-0.2	156,170	7.7		
	mod-down		160,921	189,414	17.7	192,828	19.8	215,055	33.6		
	mod-up		230,344	270,672	17.5	291,335	26.5	410,179	78.1		
	mult-eval-key		105,223	126,667	20.4	127,499	21.2	345,138	228.0		
	mult-without-rescale		526,317	714,183	35.7	708,397	34.6	1,121,405	113.1		
	relinearize		509,585	601,956	18.1	654,125	28.4	989,397	94.2		
	rescale		44,079	45,975	4.3	46,704	6.0	50,962	15.6		
	rotate-left		511,162	609,198	19.2	625,590	22.4	1,001,289	95.9		
	tensor		31,126	39,489	26.9	40,446	29.9	76,272	145.0		
	CKKS		decode	ST19	1,474	1,825	23.8	1,453	-1.4	1,434	-2.7
			decrypt		1,668	1,612	-3.4	1,976	18.5	2,036	22.1
			decrypt & decode		1,826	1,841	0.8	2,172	18.9	3,716	103.5
decrypt-sum		6,964	9,898		42.1	10,391	49.2	10,529	51.2		
encode & encrypt-symkey		35,039	32,787		-6.4	40,874	16.7	40,894	16.7		
encode & encrypt-pubkey		23,376	23,610		1.0	25,907	10.8	35,122	50.2		
encode		2,552	2,934		15.0	2,540	-0.5	4,430	73.6		
encrypt-symkey		26,459	25,652		-3.1	29,054	9.8	24,908	-5.9		
encrypt-pubkey		20,145	18,652		-7.4	19,561	-2.9	22,067	9.5		
mod-down		11,764	13,073		11.1	13,285	12.9	14,940	27.0		
mod-up		88,511	85,573		-3.3	90,122	1.8	112,336	26.9		
mult-eval-key		60,444	85,125		40.8	84,960	40.6	317,673	425.6		
mult-without-rescale		207,271	233,058		12.4	239,029	15.3	542,971	162.0		
relinearize		201,339	227,259		12.9	229,886	14.2	525,807	161.2		
rescale		5,558	6,476		16.5	6,273	12.9	6,298	13.3		
rotate-left	201,693	224,865	11.5	189,458	-6.1	547,565	171.5				
tensor	4,784	6,608	38.1	7,008	46.5	9,445	97.4				
CKKS	decode	ST7	1,531	1,433	-6.4	1,605	4.8	1,460	-4.6		
	decrypt		1,138	677	-40.5	659	-42.1	688	-39.5		
	decrypt & decode		1,714	1,667	-2.7	1,778	3.7	2,384	39.1		
	decrypt-sum		2,673	4,150	55.3	4,089	53.0	3,752	40.4		
	encode & encrypt-symkey		13,689	13,083	-4.4	16,364	19.5	14,267	4.2		
	encode & encrypt-pubkey		9,647	9,893	2.6	9,970	3.3	11,644	20.7		
	encode		1,470	1,440	-2.0	1,474	0.3	1,754	19.3		
	encrypt-symkey		10,585	10,878	2.8	11,845	11.9	10,205	-3.6		
	encrypt-pubkey		7,783	7,697	-1.1	7,813	0.4	7,979	2.5		
	mod-down		6,203	7,501	20.9	7,908	27.5	8,415	35.7		
	mod-up		6,144	7,002	14.0	7,117	15.8	10,165	65.4		
	mult-eval-key		3,790	5,189	36.9	5,213	37.5	10,969	189.4		
	mult-without-rescale		20,470	24,339	18.9	23,994	17.2	37,471	83.1		
	relinearize		18,441	21,624	17.3	21,793	18.2	32,599	76.8		
	rescale		1,942	1,793	-7.7	1,962	1.0	2,038	4.9		
rotate-left	19,508	22,260	14.1	21,715	11.3	33,775	73.1				
tensor	1,862	2,594	39.3	2,703	45.2	3,231	73.5				
BFV	decrypt & decode	n=4096	141	189	34.0	187	32.6	175	24.1		
	encode & encrypt-pubkey		637	682	7.1	661	3.8	704	10.5		
	FastBConvSk		65	67	3.1	69	6.2	67	3.1		
	FastFloor		52	54	3.8	58	11.5	54	3.8		
	mult (w/o relinearize)		1,273	1,720	35.1	1,695	33.2	1,620	27.3		
	SmMRQ		48	50	4.2	49	2.1	48	0.0		
BFV	decrypt & decode	n=16384	1,950	2,926	50.1	2,709	38.9	2,639	35.3		
	encode & encrypt-pubkey		4,614	5,544	20.2	5,223	13.2	8,621	86.8		
	FastBConvSk		1,925	1,996	3.7	1,850	-3.9	2,003	4.1		
	FastFloor		1,684	2,024	20.2	1,756	4.3	1,741	3.4		
	mult (w/o relinearize)		32,303	42,897	32.8	43,211	33.8	43,757	35.5		
	SmMRQ		572	706	23.4	569	-0.5	566	-1.0		
Average					12.3		14.2		59.6		

Table 6. On the device Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6248 CPU @ 2.50GHz with 1TB RAM, single thread speed of operations after sequentially disabling three optimizations: (1) finding the best loop optimization strategy (Sec. 6.3), (2) relaxing the modulus policy (Sec. 6.1), and (3) loop fusion (Sec. 6.2). All wall time values are expressed in microseconds (μ s), except for the slowdowns (%).

Scheme	Operation	Parameter	HEaaN.MLIR		Disabling (1)		Disabling (1), (2)		Disabling (1), (2), (3)	
			Wall time	Slowdown (%)	Wall time	Slowdown (%)	Wall time	Slowdown (%)	Wall time	Slowdown (%)
HEaaN.MLIR	decode		12,009	11,909	-0.8	12,008	-0.0	11,947	-0.5	
	decrypt		12,728	12,843	0.9	12,924	1.5	12,969	1.9	
	decrypt & decode		12,004	12,825	6.8	12,718	5.9	12,641	5.3	
	decrypt-sum		103,978	127,396	22.5	129,886	24.9	129,938	25.0	
	encode & encrypt-symkey		294,385	294,522	0.0	298,872	1.5	299,340	1.7	
	encode & encrypt-pubkey		416,706	431,726	3.6	437,352	5.0	437,287	4.9	
	encode		20,459	20,722	1.3	20,643	0.9	20,423	-0.2	
	encrypt-symkey		176,460	174,095	-1.3	219,817	24.6	220,178	24.8	
	encrypt-pubkey	FVa	310,922	311,187	0.1	312,271	0.4	312,271	0.4	
	mod-down		373,932	415,225	11.0	421,895	12.8	422,353	12.9	
	mod-up		548,177	609,960	11.3	643,747	17.4	648,360	18.3	
	mult-eval-key		101,340	152,199	50.2	151,692	49.7	152,007	50.0	
	mult-without-rescale		1,141,791	1,230,242	7.7	1,356,327	18.8	1,357,930	18.9	
	relinearize		1,060,810	1,176,853	10.9	1,256,202	18.4	1,254,831	18.3	
	rescale		99,211	100,779	1.6	102,786	3.6	102,924	3.7	
	rotate-left		1,045,842	1,215,621	16.2	1,243,129	18.9	1,241,399	18.7	
	tensor		41,516	41,727	0.5	46,430	11.5	46,445	11.9	
CKKS	decode		2,494	2,493	-0.0	2,473	-0.8	2,480	-0.6	
	decrypt		2,185	2,159	-1.2	2,154	-1.4	2,161	-1.1	
	decrypt & decode		2,583	2,771	7.3	2,778	7.5	2,776	7.5	
	decrypt-sum		15,801	19,572	23.9	20,049	26.9	20,053	26.9	
	encode & encrypt-symkey		46,680	46,645	-0.1	47,394	1.5	47,301	1.3	
	encode & encrypt-pubkey		60,367	62,723	3.9	63,708	5.5	63,624	5.4	
	encode		3,496	3,526	0.9	3,503	0.2	3,509	0.4	
	encrypt-symkey		28,881	28,983	0.4	36,512	26.4	36,541	26.5	
	encrypt-pubkey	ST19	46,829	46,782	-0.1	47,093	0.6	47,149	0.7	
	mod-down		32,902	33,545	2.0	34,289	4.2	34,152	3.8	
	mod-up		280,164	281,400	0.4	280,723	0.2	280,804	0.2	
	mult-eval-key		68,534	111,470	62.6	113,089	65.0	112,233	63.8	
	mult-without-rescale		420,117	437,575	4.2	470,139	11.9	471,241	12.2	
	relinearize		415,627	428,832	3.2	461,372	11.0	461,877	11.1	
	rescale		14,820	15,120	2.0	15,314	3.3	15,356	3.6	
	rotate-left		414,990	430,656	3.8	462,657	11.5	462,969	11.6	
	tensor		6,742	6,706	-0.5	7,596	12.7	7,572	12.3	
BFV	decode		2,445	2,429	-0.7	2,441	-0.2	2,439	-0.2	
	decrypt		960	964	0.4	964	0.4	958	-0.2	
	decrypt & decode		2,610	2,780	6.5	2,781	6.6	2,781	6.6	
	decrypt-sum		6,302	7,819	24.1	8,027	27.4	8,028	27.4	
	encode & encrypt-symkey		19,584	19,518	-0.3	19,876	1.5	19,923	1.7	
	encode & encrypt-pubkey		25,924	26,950	4.0	27,260	5.2	27,397	5.7	
	encode		1,927	1,933	0.3	1,986	3.1	1,925	-0.1	
	encrypt-symkey		11,822	11,757	-0.5	14,891	26.0	14,809	25.3	
	encrypt-pubkey	ST7	20,104	20,124	0.1	20,184	0.4	20,211	0.5	
	mod-down		19,369	20,966	8.2	21,481	10.9	21,396	10.5	
	mod-up		19,055	20,406	7.1	21,176	11.1	21,132	10.9	
	mult-eval-key		4,147	6,562	58.2	6,540	57.7	6,554	58.0	
	mult-without-rescale		45,157	51,330	13.7	52,949	17.3	52,879	17.1	
	relinearize		42,755	48,152	12.6	49,331	15.4	49,306	15.3	
	rescale		5,730	5,890	2.8	6,016	5.0	6,005	4.8	
	rotate-left		43,156	48,655	12.7	49,980	15.8	50,095	16.1	
	tensor		2,693	2,681	-0.4	3,057	13.5	3,053	13.4	
BFV	decrypt & decode		443	470	6.1	491	10.8	491	10.8	
	encode & encrypt-pubkey		1,005	1,002	-0.3	1,002	-0.3	999	-0.6	
	FastBConvSk	n=4096	115	115	0.0	119	3.5	119	3.5	
	FastFloor		90	90	0.0	95	5.6	96	6.7	
	mult (w/o relinearize)		3,898	3,909	0.3	4,045	3.8	4,039	3.6	
	SmMRQ		54	54	0.0	55	1.9	55	1.9	
	decrypt & decode		6,250	6,750	8.0	7,052	12.8	7,166	14.7	
	encode & encrypt-pubkey		10,579	11,238	6.2	11,044	4.4	11,149	5.4	
	FastBConvSk	n=16384	3,570	3,560	-0.3	3,398	-4.8	3,396	-4.9	
	FastFloor		2,973	2,964	-0.3	3,064	3.1	3,051	2.6	
mult (w/o relinearize)		71,870	81,716	13.7	81,878	13.9	83,238	15.8		
SmMRQ		642	639	-0.5	642	0.0	643	0.2		
Average					6.9		10.7		10.7	

Table 7. On the device AMD Ryzen Threadripper 2990WX with 128GB RAM, single thread speed of operations after sequentially disabling three optimizations: (1) finding the best loop optimization strategy (Sec. 6.3), (2) relaxing the modulus policy (Sec. 6.1), and (3) loop fusion (Sec. 6.2). All wall time values are expressed in microseconds (μ s), except for the slowdowns (%).